

Investigation of Quasi-Static Penetration Test Behavior of Polyurethane Foam-Filled Sandwich Composites

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Abstract

Sandwich-structured composites are preferred in applications where material strength is crucial, and they also absorb the energy of external impacts on the material. Sandwich-structured samples were manufactured by filling polyurethane foam between PVC foam sheets as the core material. Glass fiber-reinforced epoxy composite sheets used as the surface layers. In this study, the quasi-static perforation behavior of polyurethane foam-filled composite materials with same core thicknesses but different speed and penetrator was investigated. PVC with 10mm thickness was used and glass fibers with 1 mm thickness reinforced epoxy sheets used as the surface sheet material. These composite materials produced using the vacuum infusion method. The upper and lower PVC parts of the samples to be tested were cut into squares with a side length of 500 mm. The interior was then filled with polyurethane foam, leaving no gaps, and a sandwich structure was built using strong adhesive. After drying for 24 hours, the samples were chopped into 100x100 mm dimensions using a chainsaw and semi-static perforation tests were performed using a Shimadzu testing device with two speeds and two penetrator types. In quasi-static perforation tests, it was observed that the flat penetrator type absorbs more energy than the hemispherical penetrator at the same speed. If the penetrator types are same, it was observed the absorbed energy at the hemispherical penetrator is not affected much from speed. It was concluded that more energy is absorbed by the flat penetrator with lower speed.

Keywords: Sandwich composite, quasi static, pvc, polyurethane

Introduction

Metal or fiber-reinforced composite plates are used for the bottom and top layers of a sandwich structure. Materials with characteristics like energy absorption and impact resistance are used in the core section [1]. The usage of sandwich composites in the production of air, land, and sea vehicles has significantly increased due to their high energy dissipation against impacts [2], flexural resistance, lightweight and high strength [3]. When previous studies are examined, it is known that the core part of the sandwich composite absorbs energy, thus dissipating the high energy of the impact [4]. Also by placing a lightweight core (like foam, honeycomb etc.) between two strong face sheets, the second moment of area of the panel is enhanced with minimal added weight. This results in an efficient structure capable of withstanding bending and buckling loads [5].

Polyurethane foam was selected as the core material, while glass fiber reinforced sheets were evaluated for the plates that would be used on the upper and bottom surfaces. The reason of glass fibers are used over for creating composite materials because they provide significant benefits like high strength, light weight, and impact resistance [6].

In Djele and Karakuzu [7], the absorbed energy and force-deflection curves were examined by using quasi-static indentation loading in two different fiber-reinforced epoxy composites. Carbon-Kevlar hybrid fabrics and S2 glass fabrics were utilized as reinforcements. In the quasi-static indentation test, crosshead speeds were gradually increased from 1 mm/min to 60 mm/min. As the speed increased, there was a noticeable rise in absorbed energy. For instance, when the crosshead speed went from 1 mm/min to 60 mm/min, the absorbed energy increased from 42 J to 62 J at 23°C and from 33 J to 69 J at 40°C. However, at 60°C and 80°C, there wasn't a significant change in absorbed energy despite the increase in crosshead speed.

In their research, Hongyang Wang et al. [8] demonstrated that the core thickness significantly influences quasi-static perforation result. In sandwich structures, it has been observed that increasing the thickness of the core compared to the thickness of the panel plate positively affects energy

absorption. While the absorbed energy is directly related to the increase in the core thickness, it is not fully understood what effect it has on the change in the thickness of the panel plate.

Salami (2013), performing quasi-static penetration tests on sandwich composites created using polyurethane and PVC foam core materials and E-glass fiber composite surface sheets, observed that as the core thickness decreases, the composites become stiffer, resulting in increased impact contact forces. Additionally, due to the higher compressive strength of PVC compared to PUR, the compressibility of PVC is lower than PUR at the same load level. Therefore, they observed that the deformation of the top surface sheet of the PVC specimen due to bending is more limited compared to PUR, and they attributed the reason for PVC foam being less deformed than PUR foam to its higher core density and rigidity. They also noted an increase in strain as the test speed increased.[9]

This study investigates the quasi-static perforation behavior of sandwich composite structures with an outer layer made of glass-epoxy and a core material of polyurethane foam. The behavior of the produced composite structures has been examined against different penetrator and velocities. Quasi-static perforation tests were conducted for each penetrator type and velocity, and the corresponding graphs were plotted.

Methodology

Materials

In this study, AIREX PVC foam (Table 1) with thicknesses of 10 mm was employed. The upper and lower face sheets were manufactured using E-glass fiber woven laminate, featuring a density of 900 g/m². In the bonding process, a matrix material was formed by combining epoxy resin (F-1564) and epoxy hardener (F3487) in a 1/3 ratio.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of the core materials. Typical properties for AIREX® C71.55. (<https://www.3accorematerials.com>)

		Unit (metric)	Value ¹⁾	C71.55
Density	ISO 845	kg/m ³	Average <i>Typ. Range</i>	60 54 - 69
Compressive strength perpendicular to the plane	ISO 844	N/mm ²	Average <i>Minimum</i>	0.95 0.85
Compressive modulus perpendicular to the plane	DIN 53421	N/mm ²	Average <i>Minimum</i>	70 60
Tensile strength in the plane	ISO 527 1-2	N/mm ²	Average <i>Minimum</i>	1.5 1.0
Tensile modulus in the plane	ISO 527 1-2	N/mm ²	Average <i>Minimum</i>	42 30
Shear strength	ISO 1922	N/mm ²	Average <i>Minimum</i>	0.93 0.70
Shear modulus	ASTM C393	N/mm ²	Average <i>Minimum</i>	21.5 18
Shear elongation at break	ISO 1922	%	Average <i>Minimum</i>	25 15

Figure 1. (a) PVC Foam

(b) Glass Fabric Fiber Woven

Manufacturing

To obtain a sandwich structure firstly PVC foams of 1000x1000 cm dimensions were cut into 100x100 cm pieces. The height of the polyurethane was adjusted with the help of 10 mm wide and 5 mm high PVC foams and strong adhesive on the edges of the PVC foams. After obtaining the composite structure, these regions were cut and sorted. Gaps were left at the edges to prevent excessive expansion of the polyurethane, as shown in Figure 2. The bottom and top plates of the composite structure to be obtained consist of 10 mm high PVC foam, and the core consists of 5 mm thick polyurethane foam. This structure was left at room temperature under suitable pressure for 24 hours to allow the polyurethane foam to spread and expand. After 24 hours, holes were drilled at the cutting points on the upper and lower plates for better resin distribution. In this way, the sandwich structure was obtained.

Figure 2. Manufacturing of sandwich structure

After the sandwich structure production process was completed the composite to be obtained consists of a 3-layer structure with glass fiber, peeling fabric, vacuum net. Once all layers are prepared on the surface of the composite production device, they are wrapped with vacuum sealing tape and a vacuum bag.

The resin inlet and the vacuum channel are airtightly connected to both sides of the vacuum bag as seen in Figure 3. Pipes placed on both sides are carefully sealed with the vacuum bag. After evacuating the air from the system, leak checks are performed using spiral hoses. If there is no air leak after checking, the epoxy hardener mixture is prepared. The hardener is added at the rate of 1/3 of the epoxy. After the resin has been evenly spread across the entire material and cured at 80°C for 10 hours, the composite structure is produced. Subsequently, this composite material is cut into 100x100 mm² dimensions using the saw shown in Figure 3, preparing it for the quasi-static experiment.

Figure 3. Manufacturing of composite structure

Quasi Static Test

All the tests were conducted at the Composite Research Laboratory of Dokuz Eylül University using a SHIMADZU testing machine with a 100 kN capacity. In the quasi-static tests, flat and hemispherical cylindrical penetrators with a diameter of 12.70 mm were employed. Additionally, quasi static tests were performed at 2 different speeds for each penetrator.

Figure 4. (a) Shimadzu quasi static testing machine (b) Test apparatus

Figure 5. (a) Hemispherical penetrator (b) Flat penetrator

Results

In this research, we conducted quasi-static tests at speeds of 1.25 mm/min and 5 mm/min. Each test was replicated twice, and the average of these two repetitions was utilized to generate plots illustrating the relationship between contact force and deformation over time, as well as absorbed energy-deformation plots. Figure 6 illustrates graphs comparing the contact force and deformation of samples with the same core thickness, using both a hemispherical penetrator and a flat penetrator, at different speeds.

Figure 6. Force-deformation graphs for two different penetrators at speeds of 1.25 mm/min and 5 mm/min

Figure 7. Absorbed energy-deformation graphs for two different penetrators at speeds of 1.25 mm/min and 5 mm/min

In Table 2 and Figure 8, the maximum contact forces at the determined speeds are given for both penetrators. As a result, the contact force increases in the flat penetrator type compared to the hemispherical penetrator type. In addition, according to the test results, as the speed increases, the contact force also increases.

Table 2. Maximum contact force

Quasi Static Test Speed [mm/min]	Max. contact force [N] (Hemispherical penetrator)	Max. contact force [N] (Flat penetrator)
1,25	1369,699	2584,044
5	1676,051	2918,561

Figure 8. Maximum contact force diagram by speed and penetrator type

Figure 9 depicts the absorbed energy-time graphs of composites tested at different speeds and with two different types of penetrators. The flat type absorbs more energy than the hemispherical penetrator at the same speed. When the penetrator types are the same, even if the speeds are different, the energy absorbed by the semi-spherical penetrator is not significantly affected. However, at the end of the experiment, it was observed that at the same deformation level, the one with lower speed in the flat penetrator absorbed much more energy.

Figure 9. Energy - Time diagrams of by same speed and different penetrator types

Conclusions

In this study, the quasi-static behavior of a sandwich composite consisting of polyurethane foam and glass fiber-epoxy composite plates with the same core thicknesses was experimentally investigated. Both hemispherical and flat penetrators were used in the experiments, and quasi-static tests were conducted at two different speeds. The obtained results are as follows:

- In the experiment conducted with the flat indenter, the maximum contact force at a speed of 1.25 mm/min is 1.5 times greater than that of the experiment conducted with the hemispherical indenter. Additionally, the maximum contact force increases proportionally with speed.
- For the hemispherical indenter, the absorbed energy does not change with speed, but for the flat indenter, the absorbed energy is observed to increase 2.5 times at both speeds compared to the hemispherical indenter.
- The absorbed energy value for the flat indenter is observed to be more significantly affected by speed.

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